

macrophage colony-stimulating factor or colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1 / M-CSF) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : CSF1/M-CSF is a secreted cytokine which causes hematopoietic stem cells to differentiate into macrophages. It is one of the three experimentally described colony-stimulating factors and binds to the colony stimulating factor 1 receptor (CSF1R). It has been implicated in Tenosynovial giant cell tumor, knee osteoarthritis, intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma, obstructive colorectal cancer, pancreatic cancer, adult-onset leukoencephalopathy, chronic renal failure, chronic kidney disease and Triple-negative breast cancer, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of CSF1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed

*ML dicoveries of CSF1 synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

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by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: CSF1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. colony stimulating factor 1 / macrophage colony-stimulating factor (CSF1 / M-CSF)

Glycoproteins contain oligosaccharide (sugar) chains covalently attached to amino acid side-chains. The carbohydrate is attached to the protein in a co/post-translational modification via the process known as glycosylation. Secreted extracellular proteins are often glycosylated. There are various types of glycosylation, namely - N-glycosylation, O-glycosylation, P-glycosylation, C-glycosylation, S-glycosylation, glypiation, and glycation.

Colony stimulating factors (CSFs) are secreted glycoproteins which bind to receptor proteins on the surfaces of committed progenitors in the bone marrow. There they activate intracellular signaling pathways that can cause the cells to proliferate and differentiate into a specific kind of blood cell.

The colony stimulating factor 1 or macrophage colony-stimulating factor (CSF1 / M-CSF), is a secreted cytokine protein which causes hematopoietic stem cells (stem cells that give rise to other blood cells via the process of haematopoiesis which is the formation of blood cellular components) to differentiate into macrophages (type of white blood cell of the innate immune system that envelope and digest pathogens, like microbes, cancer cells, foreign substances and cellular debris, which do not have proteins that are specific to healthy body cells on their surface) or other related cell types. It is one of the three experimentally described CSFs and CSF1/M-CSF binds to the colony stimulating factor 1 receptor.

It is known that CSFs stimulate the differentiation of immature precursor cells to mature granulocytes and macrophages. Stanley [13] used purified ^{125}I -labeled murine L cell CSF to develop a radioimmunoassay (RIA) that detects a subclass of CSFs that stimulates macrophage production.

Das et al. [14] developed a murine radioreceptor assay (RRA; a laboratory technique to measure the concentration of a specific substance, via its ability to bind to its receptor in a sample) by using the high affinity interactions between pure ^{125}I -L cell colony stimulating factor and its receptor(s) on the murine macrophage cell line J774. They observed that the murine RRA selectively detected a CSF subclass (CSF1) previously defined by murine radioimmunoassay (RIA), proposed by Stanley [13]. They found that the murine CSF1 RRA failed to detect a variety of other CSF subclasses, growth factors, and hormones, while in contrast to data obtained with the murine CSF1 RIA, human CSF1 was detected by the mouse CSF1 RRA almost as sensitively as murine CSF1.

Das et al. [15] described the partial purification of human urinary CSF1 to approximately $4 * 10^6$ U/mg protein from large volumes of human urine. They observed that the carrier-free iodination of the partially purified preparation and subsequent receptor binding and elution of the resulting ^{125}I -CSF1 yielded ^{128}I -CSF1 (which was free of contaminating ^{125}I -proteins). This ^{125}I -CSF1 (approximately $4 * 10^7$ U/mg of iodinated protein) was biologically active and used to develop a RIA that specifically detected the human CSF subclass that stimulates macrophage production (CSF1). They pointed that there were at least 3 human CSF subclasses, namely ● CSF1, which stimulated the formation of colonies containing macrophages by murine and human hemopoietic cells; ● another subclass which stimulated the formation of colonies (possibly containing neutrophils, eosinophils, and macrophages) by human but not murine hemopoietic cells; and ● a third subclass that stimulated the formation of colonies (possibly containing neutrophils and macrophages) by both human and murine hemopoietic cells. Finally, they observed that the average level of CSF1 in the serum of 14 normal adult humans, as determined by RIA, was 174 ± 76 U/ml (approximately 40 pM).

Kawasaki et al. [16] isolated complementary DNA (cDNA) clones that encoded human CSF1. They observed that CSF1 appeared to be encoded by a single-copy gene, however its expression resulted in the synthesis of several messenger RNA species, ranging in size from about 1.5 to 4.5 kilobases.

1.3. Roles of CSF1 in different disease

Tenosynovial giant cell tumor (TGCT) is a rare soft tissue neoplasm with aggressive local growth and is driven by excessive CSF1 expression in tumor cells. Targeted therapy against CSF1R is an effective treatment approach for unresectable, symptomatic TGCT and Vimseltinib, an inhibitor of CSF1R, has shown clinical efficacy in patients with TGCT. Kisielewska and Rutkowski [17] outlined the pathogenesis and therapeutic options for TGCT, along with a detailed profile of vimseltinib which included its mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics, efficacy and safety data from clinical studies.

Huang et al. [18] investigated the serum and synovial fluid levels of CSF1 in patients with **knee osteoarthritis (KOA)**. For this, they selected 143 patients with KOA who received treatment. Compared to healthy volunteers, they found that KOA patients exhibited high levels of serum CSF1, IL-6/1 β , CRP, and HIF1 α . Further, the advanced group of KOA patients were observed to have higher levels of serum and synovial fluid CSF1 compared to the early group. Additionally, CSF1 stimulation increased the expression of CSF1R, IL-6/1 β , TNF α , HIF1 α , and MMP3 in macrophages. Lastly, synovial fluid and serum CSF1, synovial fluid HIF1 α , and synovial fluid IL-6 were identified as risk factors for advanced KOA.

CSF1 and TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL) have been indicated as prognostic factors in **intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma (iCCA)**. Akiki et al. [19] aimed to externally validate CSF1 and TRAIL as preoperative prognostic markers for patients with resectable iCCA. For this, they included 61 patients with resection for iCCA. They found CSF1 association with both overall survival (OS) (hazard ratio [HR] 1.03, 95 % confidence interval [CI] 1.01-1.05) and disease-free survival (DFS) (HR 1.02, 95 % CI 1.00-1.04). Further, median OS was 8 months for patients with CSF1 levels in the upper quartile (≥ 158 pg/mL), compared with the overall median OS of 47 months.

Obstructive colorectal cancer (OCRC) is hard and exhibits increased tumor budding and proliferation of myofibroblasts compared with non-obstructive CRC, thus suggesting that the occurrence of obstruction may be related to extracellular matrix (ECM) remodeling. Deng et al. [20] found that CRC and OCRC samples differed substantially in ECM composition, specifically in collagen (newly formed and mature) and proteoglycans (including glycosaminoglycan, hyaluronic acid, and chondroitin sulfate). They found that OCRC samples presented an increase in matrix cancer-associated fibroblasts (mCAF). Their abundance correlated with the accumulation of palmitic acid (PA), and it was observed that high concentrations of PA increased the secretion of ECM-related proteins by mCAFs. Further, they found that PA did not directly affect normal fibroblasts but activated the NF- κ B pathway in tumor cells to stimulate secretion of CSF1, TGF β 1, and CXCL8 (which promote the activation of normal fibroblasts into mCAFs and exacerbated ECM stiffening).

A highly suppressive tumor immune microenvironment and nonspecific target endow malignant tumors with CAR-T cells. CSF1R is highly expressed on **pancreatic cancer** tissues compared with normal tissues in GEPIA database and M2 macrophages mainly contributing to the suppressive tumor microenvironment (TME), suggesting that CSF1R is a suitable antigen. Since CSF1 is the natural ligand of CSF1R, Zhu et al. [21] constructed a CSF1-CAR and tested its cytotoxic effect on tumor cells and

macrophages in vitro. Their results showed that CSF1-CAR-T cells could lyse tumor cells dependent on CSF1R expression. They also observed that CSF1-CAR-T lysed CSF1R+ M2 macrophages, thus suggesting that CSF1-CAR-T cells played a role in eliminating tumor cells and remodeling the TME.

Microglia, the brain's resident macrophages, depend on interleukin-34 and CSF1 for their development and maintenance, while engaging with the CSF1 receptor (CSF1R). **Adult-onset leukoencephalopathy** (a neurodegenerative disorder affecting the brain's white matter) with axonal spheroids and pigmented glia (ALSP), is caused by heterozygous pathogenic mutations in the CSF1R gene. Du et al. [22] investigated molecular mechanisms underlying ALSP on postmortem brain specimens. Their results showed a significant reduction in microglia in ALSP brains, with remaining cells exhibiting a unique activation signature. They found this reduction correlated with decreased myelinating oligodendrocytes (OLs) and increased neuropilin-2+ OLs with a stress-response and anti-apoptotic signature, driven by STAT3 and fibroblast growth factor receptor pathways. Their findings underscored microglia's crucial role in supporting OL myelination and limiting astrocyte repair responses, thus pointing to therapeutic strategies balancing CSF1R, fibroblast growth factor receptor and STAT3 pathways for ALSP and other genetically caused microgliopathies.

Since M-CSF is essential for the activation of several functions of monocytes and macrophages and their production of various cytokines, Le Meur et al. [23] investigated its involvement in patients with **chronic renal failure** (CRF). When measured by ELISA, they found M-CSF serum levels being significantly higher in patients with progressive CRF and those on hemodialysis (HD) and continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis (CAPD) than in controls. Their results suggested that M-CSF might play a role in altering the immune system in uremic patients.

Acute kidney injury (AKI) can lead to **chronic kidney disease** (CKD). Yao et al. [24] established a detailed single-cell atlas of mononuclear macrophages from the onset of AKI through its progression to CKD and their results indicated that a macrophage subset with high CD38 expression was closely linked to renal fibrosis, following AKI in both mouse model and AKI patients. These CD38^{hi} macrophages, derived from resident macrophages via CSF1 signaling, secreted the NAD-depleting enzyme CD38, thus inducing senescence in renal tubular cells and promoting chronic inflammation and renal fibrosis. Their knock out of CD38 in macrophages led to increase renal NAD levels, thus reducing senescence and fibrotic responses.

Liu et al. [25] found circular RNA named circATP5C1 to have predictive function in prognosis of **Triple-negative breast cancer** (TNBC) patients. Further, they found that mechanistically, CSF1 was a downstream gene regulated by circATP5C1. Due to the interaction between circATP5C1 and insulin-like growth factor 2 mRNA binding protein 2 (IGF2BP2), they validated the alteration of CSF1 expression level. Their rescue experiments showed that circATP5C1 accelerated the progression of TNBC partly via binding with IGF2BP2 to increase the secretion of CSF1. Thus their study uncovered a novel mechanism of circATP5C1/IGF2BP2/CSF1 pathway in regulating progression of TNBC.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations

via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [26] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [27] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [27].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [28]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [29], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [26] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [26]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [30], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. CSF1 related synergies

Note - CSF1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and FDR ≤ 0.001 , in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of CSF1 were recorded.

3.1.1. CSF1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with CSF1 showed high rankings - semaphorin 3F (SEMA3F), CD38 molecule (CD38), C-C motif chemokine ligand 26 (CCL26), CD4 molecule (CD4), arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase (ALOX5), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), collagen type XI alpha 1 chain (COL11A1), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 3 (PTPN3), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), glypican 4 (GPC4), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), DNA meiotic recombinase 1 (DMC1), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), CD40 molecule (CD40), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), C-C motif chemokine ligand 22 (CCL22), coronin 2B (CORO2B), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), unc-5 netrin receptor B (UNC5B), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), crystallin alpha B (CRYAB), solute carrier family 35 member F2 (SLC35F2), tetraspanin 11 (TSPAN11), vanin 1 (VNN1), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), patched 2 (PTCH2), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), PHD finger protein 19 (PHF19), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), snail family transcriptional repressor 1 (SNAI1), hematopoietic cell signal transducer (HCST), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), peroxidase (PXDN), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), complement C1q like 1 (C1QL1), microtubule associated protein 1B (MAP1B), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology

domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), interleukin 11 receptor subunit alpha (IL11RA), synaptotagmin like 2 (SYTL2), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), elastin microfibril interfacier 1 (EMILIN1), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), NLR family pyrin domain containing 12 (NLRP12), forkhead associated phosphopeptide binding domain 1 (FHAD1), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), atypical chemokine receptor 2 (ACKR2), family with sequence similarity 198, member A (FAM198A), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), ankyrin 2 (ANK2), family with sequence similarity 105, member A (FAM105A), phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1), solute carrier family 2 member 12 (SLC2A12), LanC like family member 3 (LANCL3), ADAM metallopeptidase domain 12 (ADAM12), teneurin transmembrane protein 4 (TENM4), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3

(DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), discs, large (Drosophila) homolog-associated protein 2 / DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of CSF1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CSF1 with CSF1 – > SEMA3F / CD38 / CCL26 / CD4 / ALOX5 / COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / PTPN3 / FRY / GPC4 / SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / DMC1 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / CCL22 / CORO2B / PCOLCE / UNC5B / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB / SLC35F2 / TSPAN11 / VNN1 / PARD3B / WLS / PTCH2 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / SNAI1 / HCST / TMEM35A / FCHO1 / PXDN / LILRB2 / C1QL1 / MAP1B / MYH10 / PTPN22 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA / SYTL2 / PLCB2 / EMILIN1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / FHAD1 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / ACKR2 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / ANK2 / FAM105A / PIK3R1 / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / ADAM12 / TENM4 / ARID5B / CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / SUSD3 / MYO1E / RUNX1 / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / APBB2 / TMEM200A / TMEM71 / TVP23A / CYP2S1 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / GPR183 / MACROD2 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / YPEL2 / CABP4 / FZD8 / PDE4DIP / CSRN3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / PLAG1 / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CSF1

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CSF1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SEMA3F - CSF1	255	170	265	247	CD38 - CSF1	265	307	322	376
CCL26 - CSF1	78	283	226	299	CD4 - CSF1	306	223	246	3
ALOX5 - CSF1	210	382	94	311	COL9A2 - CSF1	225	233	258	336
COL11A1 - CSF1	261	275	277	358	TSPAN32 - CSF1	313	214	319	4
PTPN3 - CSF1	212	139	306	305	FRY - CSF1	231	263	242	273
GPC4 - CSF1	217	320	251	48	SLC23A2 - CSF1	360	314	333	385
PCSK5 - CSF1	320	274	293	381	DMC1 - CSF1	262	181	252	241
NFATC4 - CSF1	298	206	297	377	CD40 - CSF1	351	240	129	217
RIMS4 - CSF1	263	346	199	307	CCL22 - CSF1	286	246	302	285
CORO2B - CSF1	239	282	176	279	PCOLCE - CSF1	282	344	244	13
UNC5B - CSF1	307	338	335	27	PMP22 - CSF1	183	280	323	341
TRIM2 - CSF1	345	279	249	23	CRYAB - CSF1	232	345	259	295
SLC35F2 - CSF1	174	316	204	322	TSPAN11 - CSF1	236	268	205	304
VNN1 - CSF1	21	215	312	327	PAR3 - CSF1	270	248	301	361
WLS - CSF1	244	336	294	383	PTCH2 - CSF1	297	162	238	298
NRP2 - CSF1	271	331	321	2	C1orf198 - CSF1	334	271	280	333
PHF19 - CSF1	119	332	326	337	CRISPLD1 - CSF1	300	361	291	366
CCR2 - CSF1	145	228	230	349	PLAU - CSF1	281	179	264	354
BHLHE41 - CSF1	322	323	305	33	SNAI1 - CSF1	211	260	239	67
HCST - CSF1	248	213	221	332	TMEM35A - CSF1	279	234	314	340
FCHO1 - CSF1	272	380	310	43	PXDN - CSF1	169	289	289	212
LILRB2 - CSF1	234	200	269	28	C1QL1 - CSF1	65	292	272	328
MAP1B - CSF1	220	165	274	300	MYH10 - CSF1	330	376	243	18
PTPN22 - CSF1	277	330	177	278	LRCH1 - CSF1	61	272	304	318
LCP1 - CSF1	309	354	330	365	ALPK3 - CSF1	153	270	253	386
ENPP2 - CSF1	295	111	231	360	IL11RA - CSF1	229	297	307	325
SYTL2 - CSF1	214	131	213	218	PLCB2 - CSF1	224	311	283	363
EMILIN1 - CSF1	267	252	328	380	CBLN3 - CSF1	149	295	334	343
FBLN5 - CSF1	259	208	303	373	IGFBP4 - CSF1	289	347	309	379
NLRP12 - CSF1	303	237	219	25	FHAD1 - CSF1	253	63	270	242
C1orf162 - CSF1	318	309	256	12	RBMS3 - CSF1	321	333	267	378
ACKR2 - CSF1	238	242	65	314	FAM198A - CSF1	204	343	245	370
CTDSPL - CSF1	338	313	181	250	ANK2 - CSF1	221	359	210	306
FAM105A - CSF1	287	266	299	324	PIK3R1 - CSF1	202	353	222	114
SLC2A12 - CSF1	228	221	109	316	LANCL3 - CSF1	254	204	31	255
ADAM12 - CSF1	226	362	149	331	TENM4 - CSF1	241	227	276	296
ARID5B - CSF1	152	319	295	384	CRIM1 - CSF1	264	257	119	351
KCNE4 - CSF1	176	251	261	348	DDAH1 - CSF1	329	363	211	392
SUSD3 - CSF1	341	300	164	388	MYO1E - CSF1	293	326	254	17
RUNX1 - CSF1	325	373	288	375	TCHH - CSF1	196	381	250	344

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between CSF1 VS Individual members.

ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic CSF1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of CSF1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CSF1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CSF1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CHCHD6 - CSF1	288	285	190	374	SIGLEC11 - CSF1	333	267	262	8
SIGLEC16 - CSF1	109	324	281	355	LRP5 - CSF1	285	249	233	46
MXRA8 - CSF1	203	278	257	352	NLRP3 - CSF1	328	341	327	11
APBB2 - CSF1	247	183	298	281	TMEM200A - CSF1	192	374	311	301
TMEM71 - CSF1	283	293	318	382	TVP23A - CSF1	258	284	317	369
CYP2S1 - CSF1	291	290	331	329	FILIP1L - CSF1	301	321	266	20
RAB31 - CSF1	314	216	287	367	VAMP5 - CSF1	316	329	237	228
CCDC126 - CSF1	250	310	316	29	GPR183 - CSF1	311	264	278	6
MACROD2 - CSF1	208	277	185	338	IL17D - CSF1	305	236	290	330
PEAK1 - CSF1	302	205	286	37	HEG1 - CSF1	296	155	207	356
HOXB2 - CSF1	266	241	81	277	YPEL2 - CSF1	347	288	153	387
CABP4 - CSF1	230	137	200	223	FZD8 - CSF1	219	302	292	335
PDE4DIP - CSF1	276	364	151	359	CSRN3 - CSF1	206	298	285	357
CIITA - CSF1	268	123	308	290	KCNE1 - CSF1	209	148	240	289
PLAG1 - CSF1	227	352	80	362	EPHB3 - CSF1	252	258	212	38
PYCR1 - CSF1	326	203	192	313	FLRT2 - CSF1	353	265	355	309
PRKG1 - CSF1	323	232	350	321	SHC4 - CSF1	367	384	370	288
CYP4X1 - CSF1	319	254	325	389	ANKRD20A5P - CSF1	388	388	384	238
RTN4RL2 - CSF1	335	318	356	19	C2orf88 - CSF1	339	253	337	319
KBTBD12 - CSF1	337	375	367	77	LDLRAD2 - CSF1	381	348	388	280
ENTPD8 - CSF1	359	342	363	293	PLAC9 - CSF1	383	368	360	79
NUGGC - CSF1	344	356	341	220	FAM180A - CSF1	387	383	387	205
STK31 - CSF1	315	166	365	372	MME - CSF1	385	387	390	216
FAM180B - CSF1	386	391	389	169	DACT3 - CSF1	362	177	372	371
ADARB1 - CSF1	363	325	339	303	C2orf27A - CSF1	355	134	332	391
CLEC9A - CSF1	356	276	375	193	DLGAP2 - CSF1	379	340	378	178
MT1F - CSF1	327	286	349	284	ITGBL1 - CSF1	245	301	371	364
MMP17 - CSF1	372	334	373	209	DLL1 - CSF1	361	303	359	63
ZNF521 - CSF1	382	389	366	237	RYR3 - CSF1	349	355	369	200
DUSP27 - CSF1	292	211	315	5	RNU6-529P - CSF1	332	229	338	53
RHOT1P2 - CSF1	384	392	392	146	PLPP4 - CSF1	376	379	374	150
SYT15 - CSF1	310	245	368	57	FAM155A - CSF1	391	349	348	76
TMEM240 - CSF1	373	328	380	294	VIT - CSF1	390	360	386	137
ANKRD20A9P - CSF1	374	357	381	143	HACD2 - CSF1	308	173	347	347
GPX3 - CSF1	365	370	376	105	HMG3P7 - CSF1	366	378	362	86
ANKRD20A11P - CSF1	377	367	377	188	TENM3 - CSF1	380	377	383	116
RFPL1S - CSF1	370	269	345	346	LINC00937 - CSF1	370	269	345	346
LINC01907 - CSF1	256	304	329	30	ITGB2-AS1 - CSF1	392	369	379	225
LMCD1-AS1 - CSF1	364	337	364	135	CYP4F29P - CSF1	389	385	391	126
ZNF883 - CSF1	357	315	343	26	SNX18P13 - CSF1	375	390	354	109

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between CSF1 VS Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t CSF1

SEMA3F / CD38 / CCL26 / CD4 / ALOX5 ...

COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / PTPN3 ...

FRY / GPC4 / SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / DMC1 ...

NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / CCL22 / CORO2B ...

PCOLCE / UNC5B / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB ...

SLC35F2 / TSPAN11 / VNN1 / PARD3B ...

WLS / PTCH2 / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PHF19 ...

CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PLAU / BHLHE41 ...

SNAI1 / HCST / TMEM35A / FCHO1 / PXDN ...

LILRB2 / C1QL1 / MAP1B / MYH10 / PTPN22 ...

LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA ...

SYTL2 / PLCB2 / EMILIN1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 ...

IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / FHAD1 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 ...

ACKR2 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / ANK2 / FAM105A ...

PIK3R1 / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / ADAM12 / TENM4 ...

ARID5B / CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / SUSD3 ...

MYO1E / RUNX1 / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 ...

SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / APBB2 ...

TMEM200A / TMEM71 / TVP23A / CYP2S1 / FILIP1L ...

RAB31 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / GPR183 / MACROD2 ...

IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / YPEL2 / CABP4 ...

FZD8 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 ...

PLAG1 / EPHB3 / PYCR1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 ...

CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 ...

KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC ...

FAM180A / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 ...

ADARB1 / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F ...

ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 ...

RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A ...

TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / GPX3 ...

HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S ...

LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 ...

CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13 CSF1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between CSF1 and Individual members.